

Quantum Ideas In $F=dp/dt$ and a Changing Index of Refraction? Part 2

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Under usual circumstances, i.e. a photon traveling in a vacuum, the notion of a spatial resolution of a photon does not arise (assuming that one does not know about photon interference). One simply focuses on $x=ct$. If one has an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction (as in Part 1) with $n_1=1$, and $n_2>1$, the photon slows down in n_2 , has the same energy E and a greater momentum $p_2 = n_2 \cdot p$, where p is the momentum in n_1 . If one considers that a photon in n_2 interacts with atoms/molecules, i.e. wastes time that could be used for travel in x , then for a given t , the photon travels a shorter distance, hence $c_2 < c$. We suggested in Part 1 that this suggests a sharper resolution in x for p_2 , due to the shorter distance which we showed was proportional to $1/p_2$. We pointed out a mathematical correspondence between the shorter distance x in n_2 and $1/p_2$. Now p_2 is a physical property of a particle, but in Part 1, we did not establish spatial resolution as a physical property. We simply noted that in n_2 , a time t is associated with a shorter x than in $n_1=1$ and that this length in n_2 is proportional to $1/p_2$. Furthermore, we did not suggest any notion of probability, only of spatial resolution.

Here we suggest that the notion of probability exists if one considers that in a given time interval t , the time wasted may occur at any point in t or in x for that matter or even at multiple points if one assumes that while the particle is interacting with an atom/molecule, it is not interacting with a force because it is not traveling in x (or is trapped in the dx of the atom and so is not translating overall in one direction. One might argue that a hit from p_2 in n_2 occurs probabilistically because of these interactions with atoms/molecules, but physically, the idea of a finite fixed number spatial resolution has not been established.

We suggest that ideas which apply for p_2 in n_2 , should also apply for a photon moving in a vacuum. After all, the photon in n_2 is described by E , c_2 and p_2 . One does not really need to know about the interactions with atoms and molecules. This would suggest that the notion of a resolution proportional to $1/p_2$ should exist in the vacuum even though one cannot assign it to interactions with molecules/atoms. Basically, the interaction with atoms/molecules in n_2 served to establish a different dt time for $F=dp/dt$, i.e. a larger one and hence a larger $dp = 2p$ (for reflection). In other words, the physical implications of a sharper spatial resolution (x smaller for a given t in n_2) was directly linked to $1/p_2$. We consider $E_2 = n_2 \cdot E$, p_2 , c_2 for a photon in n_1 and $E, p_2, c_2 = c/n_2$ for a photon in n_2 and argue that it could make sense to have physical properties of $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$.

We suggest that one may postulate a fixed value $dx = \text{constant}/p$ for resolution where constant is a fixed number. There is no longer the idea of simple proportionality. We also suggest that spatial resolution, like p , must be a physical attribute. In n_2 , we saw that a changed spatial resolution, changed p_2 (on average) from $F = dp/dt$ arose. One might argue that one really has a photon with p and c in n_2 when it is not interacting, but we suggest that this cannot be resolved. It is the p_2 photon with its changed spatial resolution which would emerge in an experiment. If a photon in a vacuum already has a fixed spatial resolution equal to \hbar/p , then shifting to p_2 in n_2 would mean a fixed physical resolution of \hbar/p_2 , but also a resolution of \hbar/p_2 in a vacuum. In other words, the idea of spatial resolution linked to \hbar/p seems to be

a statistical approach to handling a problem with the idea that one does not have infinite spatial resolution in x .

Ideas From Part 1

In Part 1, we argued that given a photon moving in a vacuum, with

$$x=ct \quad ((1))$$

one would not consider the notion of spatial resolution based on ((1)). We suggested that this notion of spatial resolution naturally arises if a photon moves from an $n_1=1$ index of refraction (vacuum) to an $n_2>n_1$ medium with atoms/molecules. Interactions occur with the atoms/molecules which do not change the photon energy E , but which waste time that could be used for travel. This means that for a time t in n_1 , the distance x traveled in n_2 is less than that in n_1 . In fact,

$$X = c/n_2 t \quad ((2))$$

Given $E=pc$ and E remaining unchanged, $p_2= n_2 * p$, where p holds in n_1 ((3))

The shorter distance in n_2 ((2)) is proportional to $1/p_2$. This is essentially what we established in Part 1. We specifically argued that for F (force) to remain constant with dt being larger n_2 due to wasted time, dp must be larger by the same factor. For reflection, $dp = 2p$ (or for $p \rightarrow p=0$) and so we argued that momentum scales in the same way as time.

As a result, a p_2 in n_2 is linked with a shorter distance, but E and p are photon properties, but distance traveled is not an intrinsic photon property. As a result, one might argue that a photon with p_2 in a vacuum would not be associated with a shorter distance. This, however, leads to a logical problem.

In n_2 , one may describe a photon by E , p_2 and c_2 , without worrying about interactions with molecules and atoms. In a vacuum, one would have E_2 , p_2 , c . For a given t in a vacuum, the photon moves ct , but in n_2 , it moves $c_2 t$ even though it has the same p_2 in both. This suggests different spatial resolutions of a photon with p_2 depending on whether p_2 existed in n_2 or $n_1=1$. The catch is that the photon in $n_1=1$ has E_2 and so one cannot use the same t in the vacuum as in n_2 with E , if one associates a time linked with E .

We pointed out in Part 1 that a spatial resolution proportional to $1/p$ should be linked with a temporal resolution linked with $1/E$ from the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px = 0 \text{ for a photon } ((4))$$

For $E_2= (n_2*p) c$, $E_2=n_2*E$ or t proportional to $1/n_2$ ((5))

One uses a time of $1/n_2$ in $n_1=1$ and $x= ct/n_2$ which is the same as $x= c_2 t = c/n_2 * t$.

The spatial resolution of a photon with p_2 in n_1 is the same as one with p_2 in n_2 due to the different time. It seems that one may actually consider temporal and spatial resolutions as properties of a photon, i.e.

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \text{ and } \Delta x = \hbar/p \quad ((6))$$

Given the close connection of ((6)) with $-Et+px$, even if it does not equal 0 as in the photon case, we suggest that ((6)) holds for a particle with rest mass.

This, we argue, is a departure from Newtonian mechanics. We saw in the treatment of interactions with atoms/molecules in n_2 , that this implies a statistical picture, i.e. one does not know at what time a photon is interacting with an atom/molecule or even at what x the atom/molecule center-of-mass exists. This leads to a probabilistic approach.

One may propose a probability which incorporates the physical properties of a temporal and spatial resolution. By stating that spatial resolution is a property of a photon/particle, we mean that it interacts with a specific physical 2-slit apparatus with slit separations about \hbar/p .

One may then propose a probability which respects spatial and time invariance (if one removes the resolution information) i.e.

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((7))$$

How does one remove the temporal and spatial resolutions based on E and p . One multiplies by the complex conjugate of ((7)), i.e. the modulus, (only part of the mathematical information of ((7))) represents spatial and temporal invariance.

Given ((7)) as a math function, one might argue for its continuity in 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction. Its derivative should also be continuous. For only refraction, one has a problem:

$$A \exp(ipx) = B \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ and } pA \exp(ipx) = p_2 B \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is contradictory, forcing one to introduce a reflected photon and write:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ip_1x) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((9a))$$

$$A \exp(ipx) - p_1 B \exp(-ip_1x) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((9b))$$

Given that an incident photon may reflect or refract, one has the equation:

$$P(\text{incident}) = 1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract}) \quad ((10))$$

((10)) is written a priori, but the results of ((9)) cannot contradict it.

This implies that in ((9a)) and ((9b)), p_1 , the reflected p magnitude must equal p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1, we argued that if one considers an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction, then a photon changes from E, p, c to $E, p_2=n_2*p, c_2= c/n_2$. If one has a time interval of t in n_1 , then $x=ct$, but in n_2 , $x_2=c_2 t = ct/n_2$. Also, from $E=pc$, $p_2=n_2*p$. As a result, there is a shorter distance for a given t in n_2 and this shorter distance is proportional to $1/p_2$. P_2 , however, is a property of a photon and we did not prove in Part 1 that the spatial interval is a fixed number and also a physical property. (By a physical property, we mean that a photon interferes with a 2-slit apparatus if the slit widths are about \hbar/p apart.)

Here, we argue that one should consider E, p_2, c_2 in n_2 with E_2, p_2, c in a vacuum. We note that $E_2=n_2*E$. If one is to have the same spatial resolution as a property in both cases, then using $-Et+px$ one may consider $1/E$ as proportional to time for a photon. Then in n_1 , $x= c E/n_2$ while in n_2 , $x= c_2 t = c/n_2 * t$. Thus, we argue for $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ which follow from $-Et+px$ and can also apply to a particle with rest mass, although one cannot use $E=pc$ and the associated arguments above.

We also argue that the n_1 - n_2 junction problem shows that in n_2 there exists the notion of probability because one does not know when or where the photon interacts with an atom/ molecule. If one assumes that the photon interaction with an atom is out-of-commission to interact with another particle, then one has a probabilistic view of interactions of p . One might suggest a uniform distribution, but one needs to enforce time and spatial resolutions are properties of the photon. This leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, we argue, if one wishes to enforce spatial and temporal invariance if the resolution information is removed. This can be seen from the modulus or from multiplying $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ by its complex conjugate.